

Exclusivity strategies of drugs: A view of bibliometric analysis based on Orange Book

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Introduction

This paper investigates how the firms of blockbuster drugs use exclusivity strategies to extend drug exclusivity in three stages of lifecycle management. The measurement of product exclusivity, patent exclusivity, and market exclusivity is based on the bibliometric data of Orange Book listed approved drugs from FDA. The research samples are 130 blockbuster drugs with annual revenue of US \$1 billion collected from the PharmaCompass database for 2015-2021 and 1164 patents extracted from the 1985-2022 Orange Book. We compare the difference among product portfolios, the patent type codes, patent portfolio, and market in three stages of the drug lifecycle to understand how the firm uses exclusivity strategies to extend drug life.

Exclusivity Strategies

Drug exclusivity acquired through various product mixes, repositioning products, and patents yield higher prices and profits for new-brand drugs. Branded-drug companies use various strategies to increase the exclusivity of their products (Song & Han, 2016).

Patent exclusivity

A new drug's patent exclusivity typically covers primary and secondary patents. The primary patent claimed the product's active pharmaceutical ingredient (API), followed by secondary patents that cover unique formulations and delivery mechanisms.

Product exclusivity

Product exclusivity (regulatory exclusivity) in the United States can be characterized into two basic types (Smith, 2011): New chemical entity (NCE) exclusivity and new use/formulation exclusivity. NCE exclusivity contains the API in the product that had never been

previously approved nor marketed and will provide the developer with five years of exclusivity. New use/formulation exclusivity is three years and includes a significant change, such as a new indication, dosage strength or form, delivery method, patient population, or condition of use.

Market exclusivity

Market exclusivity strategies that exploit regulations and expand the patent life to maintain market share or delay the introduction of generic drugs involve identifying regulations to increase market exclusivity.

Methodology

The Waxman-Hatch Act requires the listing of patents relating to each approved New Drug Application in the "Orange Book" maintained by the FDA and provides procedures to introduce generic drugs immediately upon the expiry of the patents on the drug. Orange Book published the approved drug products on the basis of safety and effectiveness by the FDA and related patent and exclusivity information. We use the data to measure various exclusivity of branded drugs, including the NDA number, product number, active ingredient(s), trade name, and expiration dates and codes associated with each patent.

Results and Implication

The results in Table 1 showed 130 blockbuster drugs, of which 86 (66%) were internal innovation drugs and 44 (34%) were external ones. The average primary patents of each blockbuster drug are 2.89, identified with drug substance and the average secondary patents are 6.4, identified with polymorphs and methods of use. The average 18.46 year guaranteed market exclusivity provided to blockbuster drugs prevents the entry of competitor drugs longer than branded drugs in Beall,

Hwang & Kesselheim's (2019) research. Comparing the average total drug lifecycle times, the pre-market period in Fig. 1—was a significant difference between internal and external innovation drugs (13.54 versus 11.59 years; $P = 0.061$). However, market exclusivity times were not different (118.66 versus 18.07 years; P

= 0.43). These data indicate that market exclusivity times are similar, although the internal innovation of blockbuster drugs is thought to be more time-consuming to develop than external innovation drugs.

Table 1. T-test of internal innovation drugs and external innovation drugs Applicants of NDA v.s. Distributors of Blockbuster Drugs.

Dimension	Variable (N=130)	Internal innovation drug (same, n=86)		External innovation drugs (different, n=44)		t-test P-value	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Pre-Market period	Pre-clinical development time	5.490	4.003	3.595	3.953	2.564	0.012**
	Clinical development time	8.046	3.901	7.991	4.035	0.075	0.941
	Pre-market development time	13.535	5.523	11.586	5.656	1.888	0.061*
Product exclusivity	No. of NDA	1.302	0.634	1.250	0.534	0.469	0.640
	No. of products	3.140	2.099	3.614	2.517	-1.138	0.257
Patent exclusivity	No. of primary patents	3.105	2.882	2.477	2.246	1.260	0.210
	No. of secondary patents	6.372	6.220	6.455	7.026	-0.068	0.946
	No. of patents in phase I	2.814	2.614	1.523	1.406	3.661	0.000***
	No. of patents in phase II	4.477	5.375	4.136	4.381	0.363	0.717
Market exclusivity	No. of patents in phase III	2.221	2.888	3.273	5.939	-1.110	0.272
	Market exclusivity period	18.663	4.085	18.065	4.070	0.791	0.430

*: $p < 0.1$; **: $p < 0.05$; ***: $p < 0.01$.

Figure 1. Cumulative time distribution from first patent filing to NDA approval for internal versus external innovation drugs.

Acknowledgments

This work was financially supported by the Center for Research in Econometric Theory and Applications

(Grant no. 111L900204), which is under the Featured Areas Research Center Program by the Higher Education Sprout Project of Ministry of Education (MOE) in Taiwan, the Universities and Colleges Humanities and Social Sciences Benchmarking Project (Grant no. 111L9A002), and the National Science and Technology Council (NSTC), Taiwan, with Grant No. 111-2634-F-002-018- and 111-2410-H-020-002-MY3.

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